

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Anjulo****FIRST NAME: Marshet****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. When writing papers, one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism. Which of the following is not a plagiarism? Choose the correct answer.**
 - Taking someone else's words or ideas without citing.
 - If you take ideas from a source without footnoting the source.
 - You use the words of a source without quotation marks.
 - Cite a work you are using within the actual text itself.¹**

- 2. Giving a credit for an author is a requirement in academic writing, for this reason we need to quote in our citations, which one of the following is not correct about quotations? Choose the correct answer.**
 - Use quotation at any time when you feel important.²**

¹ Euclid University, *ACA-401 Course pack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1> (accessed March 7, 2020), 5

- Limit the use of quotations.
 - Use quotation when the authority figures is important to persuade your readers.
 - Use quotations when there is especially strong language.
3. **Which one of the following is correct about research argument? Choose the correct answer.**
- We do not need to demonstrate how we reach them.
 - Reasoning based on evidence is the only way to reach a sound conclusion.
 - We can offer intuitions or feelings as evidence for readers to evaluate.
 - You must lay out your reasons and evidence so that your readers can consider them; then you must imagine both their questions and your answers.³**
4. **When planning oral presentation, we need to consider the followings, except one? Choose the correct answer.**
- Narrow the focus, you may optionally present, problem statement, summary of sub argument and methodology or data report.
 - Understand the difference between listener and readers.

²Euclid University, 7

³ Kate L. Turabian. A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. 8th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 36.

- presenters must know that passive listeners are like active readers.**⁴
- You must plan a talk just as carefully as you would have written report.
5. **One of the following is not a reason for citing? Choose the correct answer.**
- To give credit for your own work.**⁵
- To assure readers about the accuracy of your facts.
- To show readers the research tradition that informs your work.
- To help readers follow or extend your research.
6. **A research approach is directly tied to and fits with the research problem, purpose, and research questions, which one of the following is not the primary qualitative traditions? Choose the correct answer.**
- Case control.**⁶
- Grounded Theory.
- Case study
- Phenomenology

⁴ Turabian, 80.

⁵ Turabian, 86.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 11.

7. **According to Guba and Lincoln (1998), there are various criteria for evaluating the trustworthiness of qualitative research: which one of the following is not among those criteria's? Choose the correct answer.**
- Credibility.
 - Dependability
 - Reliability and validity⁷**
 - Transferability.
8. **At the final stages of writing your dissertation, it is crucial that you once again make certain that all the necessary elements that constitute a dissertation are aligned with one another. One of the following is not a correct statement? Choose the correct answer.**
- Findings, which are Subjective, are the basis for interpretation, which are Objectives.⁸**
 - Problem statement defines the subject of inquiry.
 - Purpose addresses the research problem. Findings and interpretations together are the basis for drawing conclusions.
 - Conceptual frame work is based on research question's.
9. **According to WHO rule of guide which one of the following is not correct about footnote? Choose the correct answer.**
- Number footnotes to the text consecutively.
 - Use superscript Arabic numerals to identify footnotes.
 - Place footnotes at the bottom of the page.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 82.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 165.

They should be kept to a maximum⁹

10. Which one of the following is not correct about titles according to WHO rule of guide? Choose the correct answer.

Do not abbreviate the title

Use all capitals for formal titles.¹⁰

Do not separate the title from the name with a comma

None.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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World Health Organization (WHO), *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva, Switzerland: WHO Press, 2004 (accessed April 1, 2020).

⁹ World health organization (WHO). *WHO style guide* (Geneva, Switzerland: WHO Press, 2004), (accessed April 1, 2020), 19.

¹⁰ World health organization, 35.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.